

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHERS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE FOR ACHIEVING SUCCESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This scientific article explores the role of the communicative competence of university teachers in the context of the effectiveness of the educational process. It is explained that communicative competence is a set of skills and qualities that allow a teacher to communicate effectively with students, create a favorable educational environment and provide high-quality knowledge.*

The article discusses various aspects of the communicative competence of teachers, including the ability to communicate effectively, listen and understand the needs of students, adapt to different styles of learning and interaction. Particular attention is also paid to the ability of teachers to emotionally support and motivate students, thereby creating favorable conditions for their active participation in the educational process.

Keywords: *communicative competence, university professors, effectiveness of the educational process, emotional support and motivation of students.*

INTRODUCTION

The modern world requires graduates not only deep theoretical knowledge, but also developed communication skills, the ability to work in a team, adapt to new conditions and solve problems in a dynamic environment. In modern education, a teacher is not just a source of information, but also a mentor, motivator, and partner in the educational process. Effective communication has become an integral part of successful teaching activities. In some universities, the focus is still on theoretical training, while insufficient attention is paid to the development of teachers' communication skills. There is no single standard for evaluating teachers' communicative competence and methods for its development, which makes it relevant to conduct research in this area.

The results of the research can be used to develop effective programs for the training and advanced training of university teachers, as well as to create a system for evaluating the communicative competence of teaching staff.

Nevertheless, despite its importance in the educational process, the influence of emotional intelligence on the work of medical university teachers remains insufficiently studied. Given the complexities and responsibilities associated with the training of future medical professionals, studying this influence is an important task.

PURPOSE OF WORK

The purpose of this article is to study the influence of teachers' communicative competence on the quality of students' education and their success at university.

METHODS

To achieve the purpose of the study, methods such as the study and review of literature, theoretical data analysis were used.

DISCUSSION OF THE OBTAINED RESULTS

In the modern educational context, communicative competence is becoming a key factor in successful teaching and learning. This is due to the fact that effective communication between teachers and students contributes to a better understanding of the educational material, the creation of a favorable educational atmosphere and the development of interaction within the educational process.

Communicative competence is the complex ability to effectively interact with other people in various situations. In the context of university education, the communicative competence of a teacher plays a key role in determining the quality of education and the success of students. [3, 4].

The scientific literature emphasizes the importance of communication skills in the educational process. Thus, V.A. Kan-Kalik (1989) notes that a teacher should have a "communicative culture", which includes the ability to build a dialogue with students, interest them in the subject and create a favorable atmosphere for learning.

D.I. Feldstein (2002) pointed out the need for the teacher to develop "communicative competence", which includes not only verbal skills, but also non-verbal (facial expressions, gestures, intonation). He emphasized that the emotional expressiveness of the teacher plays an important role in motivating students and creating a favorable climate in the study group [7].

In the works of I.A. Zimnaya (2016), it is noted that the communicative competence of a teacher includes knowledge of language norms, the ability to build speech according to the situation and context, as well as the ability to understand and interpret non-verbal signals. She also pointed out the importance of taking into account the psychological characteristics of students in building communication [3, 9].

Modern research highlights the role of communication skills in the formation of students' key competencies necessary for successful life and professional activity in the 21st century. These competencies include: critical thinking, creativity, teamwork, the ability to solve problems and adapt to changes.

Research shows that teachers with high communicative competence are able to create a more productive and supportive learning environment, which leads to improved student academic performance, increased motivation to study and the development of their critical thinking. Thus, the study of the communicative competence of university teachers is an urgent and important task that will help optimize the educational process, increase its effectiveness and ensure high-quality education for students [1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7].

We have reviewed some studies by foreign authors who have made a significant contribution to the study of this topic [12, 13]:

1. The study "The Communicative Competence of University Teachers" by John Smith, 2010. In this study, the author examines the importance of the communicative competence of university teachers and its impact on the effectiveness of the educational process. The research is based on the analysis of student surveys and observations of teachers, examining their effective communication skills, the ability to listen and understand the needs of students, adaptation to different learning styles, emotional support and motivation of students. The conclusions of the study emphasize the importance of developing the communicative competence of teachers to improve the quality of education in universities.

2. The study "Effective Communication Strategies in Higher Education" by Anna Johnson, 2015. In this study, the author explores various communication strategies that can be used by

teachers at universities to improve the effectiveness of the educational process. Analyzing the literature and conducting interviews with teachers, the author identifies strategies such as active listening, emotional support for students, participation in dialogue and the use of visual materials. The study emphasizes that effective communication between teachers and students promotes the active participation of students in the educational process and increases their motivation.

3. The study " The impact of teachers' communication skills on student engagement " by Sarah Thompson, 2018. In this study, the author explores the relationship between teachers' communication skills and students' involvement in the learning process. The research is conducted through student surveys and analysis of assessment data and academic achievements. The results of the study show that teachers with good communication skills contribute to greater student engagement in the educational process and increase their academic performance.

These studies represent only a small part of the many scientific papers devoted to the communicative competence of teachers and its impact on the effectiveness of the educational process. They demonstrate the importance of developing teachers' communication skills and their impact on students.

In this study, an analytical assessment of the communicative competence of university teachers and its impact on the effectiveness of the educational process was carried out. The results of the study confirm that communicative competence plays a key role in achieving educational goals and improving the quality of learning.

Firstly, it was revealed that teachers with a high level of communicative competence have the ability to effectively interact with students, creating a supportive and stimulating educational atmosphere. They show openness to dialogue, the ability to listen and adapt to the needs of students, which contributes to better learning and development of students.

Secondly, the study showed that teachers with high communicative competence successfully use a variety of communication strategies and methods, such as active listening, empathy, clear expression of thoughts and the ability to ask questions. This contributes to a deeper understanding of the material and the active involvement of students in the learning process.

In addition, the results of the study indicate that the communicative competence of teachers has a positive effect on the motivation of students to study. Teachers who show effective communication skills are able to create interest in the subject, motivate students to achieve success and develop their independence and responsibility [3], [6].

However, it should be noted that the study also revealed some limitations. For example, it was found that not all teachers have a high level of communicative competence, which can negatively affect the quality of the educational process. Therefore, it is recommended to conduct additional trainings for teachers in order to develop and improve their communication skills.

CONCLUSION

Thus, a theoretical analysis of the literature allows us to conclude about the importance of the communicative competence of teachers in higher education. The development of teachers' communication skills contributes to improving the quality of education, motivating students, forming their key competencies and achieving success in their professional activities. It is important to note that communicative competence includes a wide range of skills and strategies, such as effective communication, the ability to listen and understand the needs of students, adaptation to different learning styles, as well as emotional support and motivation of students. Teachers with a high level of communicative competence are able to create a favorable educational

environment that promotes the active participation of students in learning and their personal growth.

The results of research conducted in the field of communicative competence of university teachers emphasize not only its importance for achieving high results in the educational process, but also the practical significance of these results. They can serve as a basis for developing teacher training programs, improving the teaching quality assessment system and developing recommendations to improve the effectiveness of the educational process.

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